

THE USEFUL SIDE OF THE ESP AS A SUBJECT TO THE LEARNERS

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In the professional training of qualified specialists for various fields, a component of language learning is ESP. There are many monographs in this area, various studies are being conducted, special educational methods have been developed, but, unfortunately, most of the developers are foreign authors. In our country, at different levels, it is said that today university graduates should have a confident command of the English language [1]. However, the level of English language proficiency among students of technical universities leaves much to be desired. The article provides a brief overview of the literature of foreign authors in this area and an attempt to distinguish between the concepts of “English for general purposes” and “English for professional purposes”.

Currently, English is a mixed language, it is assigned the role of a world language [2], therefore, knowledge of English is the path to knowledge, education, technology and scientific progress, business and international trade. Since there are several fields of activity, education, science, etc., it came to represent a type of language that could satisfy each field, thus English for Professional Purposes (ESP) came into being, which refers to teaching or learning a language for a specific field (for example, law, medicine or for business in general) [3]. Today, knowledge of a foreign language, and in particular English, is considered not only the basis for better communication, but also important a source of technological progress because it allows for the rapid exchange of information and exploration of common global problems. The development of language skills is aimed at actively expanding students' knowledge of the English language. In higher education institutions, classes and language courses always use texts for specific professional fields (architecture, business, civil engineering, electronics, ecology, management, etc.). Such professional texts, as a rule, should be focused on the communicative needs of students at a particular university. However, teaching/learning ESP involves much more than teaching English through specific materials and content. Teaching professional English combines the development of linguistic skills and the acquisition of specific information. It is believed that even homework should be related to both the specialty and the mentioned skills.

Active participation in various interdisciplinary collaborative programs at the international level requires academic knowledge, scientific competence and objective assessment of new ideas. Knowledge of English facilitates access to new information resources. It is still unclear what is meant by the phrase “English for professional purposes”. Some scholars in the field simply describe it as teaching English for any purpose that may be given. Other scholars, however, have been more precise, describing this phenomenon as teaching English for academic purposes or teaching ESP or direct use of the language at work. Below are a few definitions presented for discussion: “English for specific purposes is a term that refers to the teaching and learning of English for a specific career (for example, law, medicine or business in general, etc.” [3].

Therefore, there is a need to learn English. Mackay and Mountford define English for vocational purposes as the teaching of a language for “entirely practical purposes” [4]. Thus, it is the needs of the student that determine the purpose and content of the course program. These may be academic, professional or scientific needs. The authors also define this term as a special language that is used in specific conditions by certain participants in the situation. Richards and Platt define the term “English for specific purposes” as any type of English language associated with specific professional or educational purposes of students who have a specific vocabulary and understand specific language constructs characteristic of their area of profession [5].

The origin and development of ESP is based on the interests of students in a particular discipline, the interests of ESP leaving its own mark both in the design of curricula and in the choice of appropriate teaching methods. Based on this, we can assume that English is not a goal in the learning process, but a means to achieve another goal. In this context, Robinson and Coleman argue that students learn ESP not because they are interested in English as such, but because they have to complete a task in English. Their command of English should be such that it can be used to improve their level in the study of special disciplines [1].

From the point of view that “students know exactly why they are learning a language” [3], it is believed that students are more motivated in ESP classes than in other classes that seem to have more advantages in the process learning, while this benefit can make it easier to achieve educational goals. Moreover, students in English classes achieve the same goal for the same time, allowing teachers to more quickly meet the needs and expectations of students by saving time and effort.

Thus, the main factors in ESP classes are the students and the teaching methods or approach and what made the researchers emphasize that English for professional purposes is a method and not a product, which means that learning a language is not using it. From this point on, they pay attention to an oriented approach to teaching, “in which all decisions regarding content and method are based on the demand of the students themselves” [4].

Fixed and variable characteristics received much attention not only in the writings of Strevens, the definition of ESP was mentioned earlier, but Evans and Maggie used these characteristics when they divided the characteristic features of ESP into two groups (the constant characteristics are as follows):

1. ESP is about meeting the specific needs of students and the desire to learn;
2. ESP uses everything the methodology of the discipline it serves.

For example, English language for engineers, teaching methods can be used when studying other disciplines. English for Vocational Purposes does not focus on all language skills, but on some essential workplace skills such as grammar, vocabulary and writing [2].

We observe changing characteristics in the following five points: ESP can be related to or intended for specific disciplines (engineering, medicine, tourism, etc.); ESP has its own educational approaches, methods and objectives, which cannot always be applied in teaching general English; ESP is intended for study by those students who are seeking to acquire a specific profession, so it is quite suitable for teaching an adult audience; ESP is usually designed for intermediate to advanced students who have a good command of the English language; most courses require some basic knowledge of the language system, but beginners can also benefit from them [1].

Hutchinson and Waters do not talk about any restrictions in the levels or ages of students, they only emphasize the individual needs of students and special knowledge in using ESP [3]. Although there are several purposes and different reasons why to study English, the way of learning may always be the same. “Although the content of instruction may differ, there is no reason to believe that the mode of study should be any different for a student studying English for professional purposes and for a student studying general English”. Researchers believe that the methodology of teaching ESP “can be used in the study of any language” [4]. Having studied all these definitions, we have got a general picture that this field, as the name suggests, comes from the needs of students, learners or participants in a situation, where it has been identified that it is created to

help students use language in specific situations, areas and circumstances. Teaching ESP must meet the needs of students in its study and materials for study, as a rule, must have the characteristics of the target situation.

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